

Strengthening the Implementation of the New Pact on Migration and Asylum through Soft Enforcement

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Introduction

After two years of legal and operational preparation, the application of the New Pact on Migration and Asylum, the EU's latest reform of asylum and migration policies, commences in June 2026. The two years that intervened between the adoption of the Pact's legal instruments and their entry into application were a policy novelty. This preparatory period was intended to allow member states to appropriately prepare their national systems, including in terms of human resources and physical infrastructures, to operationalise their legal obligations. This preoccupation with implementation illustrates a higher level of policy maturity compared to previous legislative harmonisation efforts. It is also based on an understanding that not only legislative harmonisation but also administrative governance is important to ensure compliance with the new rules.

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Related to this preoccupation with governance is the rise of processes aimed at ensuring compliance, without necessarily resorting to coercion or constraint, which we conceptualise as 'soft enforcement'. Drawing on the conceptualisation of, and empirical research on, soft enforcement,¹ this Policy Brief explores the potential and limits of soft enforcement to strengthen the implementation of the New Pact.

This Policy Brief focuses on two relevant trends. The first relates to the potential and challenges of *steering*. This can be understood as the intentional shaping of implementation through tools such as guidance, hybrid coordination frameworks, operational support, and networks. The brief also explores the potential and limitations of *monitoring* processes related to the implementation of the Pact and compliance with the reformed asylum rules. This is based on a broad understanding of monitoring which includes "processes involving the systematic collection or collation of data [...] that provide indications of the extent of implementation progress, achievement of intended results [...] use of allocated funds and other important intervention and context-related information".² The Brief closes with a set of recommendations on strengthening the potential of soft enforcement as a means to enhance rights-compliant policy implementation.

Background: Implementation amid political contestation over migration management

The past decade has seen difficulties in addressing systemic weaknesses in the Common European Asylum System (CEAS) and the Schengen Area, as well as political tensions between member states. Following the limited operationalisation of the emergency intra-EU relocation schemes between 2015-17,³ the EU resorted to ad hoc, small-scale emergency relocation based on bargaining. Recurring (systemic) fundamental rights violations, such as pushbacks at the external

borders, became widespread and pointed to wider rule of law failings.⁴ Moreover, unilateral responses, such as the reintroduction of internal border controls,⁵ also became more prominent. The 2024 political and legal compromise on the New Pact therefore brought with it renewed optimism. It was, however, immediately understood that on-the-ground implementation of the agreed reforms was critical.

Yet the two-year preparatory phase for Pact implementation has cast doubts on the Pact's prospects and member states' sustained political will for its full implementation. For example, the previous Hungarian government, as well as the government of Slovakia, failed to pledge solidarity contributions in the first ever annual solidarity cycle,⁶ an integral part of the New Pact architecture. Moreover, Poland became the latest in a series of member states to temporarily suspend the right to asylum for crisis management purposes.⁷ This 'temporary' suspension has been extended continuously since March 2025.

Despite the large-scale efforts Pact implementation requires, member states are also increasingly looking beyond the Pact to address migratory challenges. As a result of this policy tendency, the Asylum Procedures Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2024/1348)⁸ was further amended in February 2026, relaxing the rules for transfers of asylum seekers to safe third countries outside the EU territory (Regulation (EU) 2026/463).⁹ Italy has sought to establish extraterritorial processing arrangements with Albania.¹⁰ More member states have called for further EU-level 'innovative solutions' linked to the externalisation of protection obligations, with openness among EU leadership.¹¹

It is against this background that soft enforcement processes are on the rise. The increase in steering processes reflects both the political sensitivity of the field, and the need for flexibility, speed, and coordination across multiple actors. The Pact's governance architecture reflects the policy salience of soft enforcement processes, with the Commission emphasising the importance of "steering, guidance and dialogue" as motors for ensuring implementation progress.¹² At the same time, the use of monitoring processes to ensure the implementation of EU migration law and policy is considerable. The next section examines both the potential and challenges inherent in soft enforcement.

State of play: Critically assessing soft enforcement through steering and monitoring

Soft enforcement through steering

Key processes embedded within the New Pact, such as the Common Implementation Plan, the European

Annual Asylum and Migration Report, and the European Migration and Asylum Strategy, constitute the most visible layers of the Pact's implementation phase and governance framework. In addition, the Commission introduced a wide range of soft instruments designed to facilitate the practical implementation of the Pact. Many of these instruments are developed, coordinated, or operationalised with EU agencies playing a central role. These steering instruments entail various levels of visibility and accessibility, with information on their design and functioning scattered.

Challenges and limitations linked to steering mechanisms

Transparency

An important challenge to ensuring transparency relates to the fragmented and opaque nature of the architecture of steering mechanisms. A first layer of opacity concerns the creation of multiple coordination platforms that play a steering role but remain only partially documented. For example, the Pact Implementation Platform introduced in 2025 acts as a central forum to steer implementation, including discussions on national planning and the strategic use of EU funding.¹³ However, no information is publicly available regarding its composition, functions, or interactions with other platforms.

Questions of visibility extend to some of the actors involved in Pact implementation. The Pact foresees the appointment of an EU Solidarity Coordinator by the Commission to oversee the implementation of the solidarity mechanism and promote a culture of preparedness among member states. While the position and its holder can be identified through DG HOME's organisational structure, relatively little public information is available regarding the practical functioning of the role, their effectiveness, or their interaction with member states. More relevant, however, is that the limited visibility of the role makes it difficult for external observers to assess how the function is being carried out in practice and how it contributes to operationalising solidarity under the Pact.

Similar ambiguity surrounds the EU Return Coordinator. The Return Coordinator is tasked with steering functions such as "bringing together the strands of EU return policy and facilitating a seamless and interlinked implementation of the return process";¹⁴ working in close coordination with the High-Level Network on Returns. While the EU Return Coordinator is presented as a key innovation of the Pact and plays an important role in the practical implementation of EU return policy, the position derives primarily from Commission policy and soft implementation documents rather than a dedicated legislative mandate.¹⁵ In practice, the Coordinator holds a strategic position for steering the implementation of returns, yet without clearly defined functions, appointment procedures, or accountability mechanisms.

This is further compounded by the High-Level Network on Returns, an informal coordination forum composed of senior national officials, EU agencies, and Commission representatives. Similarly, its functioning is explicitly based on confidential exchanges under Chatham House rules, with only short conclusions recorded instead of formal minutes. Despite reportedly contributing to Commission working documents on return policy,¹⁶ its internal deliberations and concrete influence remain largely inaccessible.

The lack of transparency is not limited to newly introduced Pact instruments but reflects a broader pattern of inconsistency in how steering mechanisms are introduced and integrated into the policymaking process over time. The Task Force Migration Management, whose creation was announced alongside the New Pact in 2020, was presented by the Commission as an initiative to ensure effective migration management. However, the Task Force is not mentioned in the Pact's core legal and policy architecture, including the Asylum and Migration Management Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2021/1060), or the Common Implementation Plan. Beyond a single webpage outlining its general purpose, little information is available on its functioning, evolution, or deliverables. This raises questions as to whether the Task Force has been replaced, absorbed into other mechanisms, or continues to operate in parallel without clear articulation.

Unclear synergies and overlaps

The Pact's implementation relies on overlapping streams of information and analysis, but the way these are combined in practice is rarely made explicit. The Commission itself has acknowledged the need to "avoid duplication, promote simplification and ensure synergies",¹⁷ including by organising joint sessions of committees alongside network meetings of relevant agencies, such as the EU Asylum Agency and Frontex. Nevertheless, the growing number of committees, networks, and coordination platforms makes it difficult to assess how these different structures interact and how their respective outputs feed into the overall governance of Pact implementation.

Overlapping structures are particularly evident in the preparation of the European Annual Asylum and Migration Report, which provides the analytical basis for the Commission Implementing Decision identifying Member States facing migratory pressure and eligible for solidarity measures. In doing so, the Commission relies on a multiplicity of parallel information streams. These include existing reporting tools such as the Integrated Situational Awareness and Analysis under the Council-led Integrated Political Crisis Response mechanism. They also draw on inputs from the Commission-led Migration Preparedness and Crisis Blueprint Network, which produces situational assessments through dedicated meetings, including those held in July and September. While being present in these fora, EU agencies generate their own assessments, includ-

ing Frontex's Annual Risk Analysis and outputs from the Risk Analysis Network.

These mechanisms often involve the same actors, namely the Commission, member states, and EU agencies, but operate through parallel frameworks with overlapping functions. The respective weight and hierarchy of these different sources remain unclear. Moreover, the Commission does not specify how competing assessments are combined into a single strategic evaluation.

Incoherent synergies are also visible in the governance of returns. The respective roles of the Return Coordinator, the High-Level Network on Returns, and Frontex are not always clearly delineated. While the Return Coordinator is tasked with ensuring coherence and coordination across return-related activities, they also chair the High-Level Network on Returns, making it difficult to distinguish between strategic steering and coordination functions. At the same time, Frontex plays a central role in operational implementation through its return support tools, programmes, and activities. The result is a governance arrangement in which strategic steering, coordination, and operational support are closely intertwined and often involve the same actors. This raises questions about the precise function of the High-Level Network on Returns, particularly whether it primarily serves as a preparatory forum, a coordination platform, or an informal decision-shaping space, as well as about how responsibility and accountability for steering outcomes are allocated across the different actors involved.

EU agencies as embedded steering actors: the example of the EU Asylum Agency

Within this layered architecture, EU agencies play an increasingly central role as embedded steering actors in migration management. While the Common Implementation Plan formally assigns them a wide range of supporting tasks during the two-year preparatory period, in practice, their role extends beyond support to encompass de facto steering functions. This can be seen in the case of the European Union Asylum Agency.

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The Asylum Agency produces a wide range of guidance and information tools that influence how member states implement asylum procedures. These include Country Guidance and Country of Origin Information (COI) information to assist member state authorities in the assessment of asylum applications. In addition, so-called Convergence Reports introduced under the Pact support member states in identifying nationalities likely to fall under border procedures.¹⁸ While these instruments

are not legally binding, they operate through procedural embedding, creating soft obligations that structure administrative behaviour across member states. This is reflected in recurring formulations in Pact legislation on EU agency actions and products, such as member states 'shall take into account', 'use as a basis for', or 'assess against'.

The agency's pivotal steering functions heighten the challenge of maintaining independence. The Asylum Agency is both institutionally and functionally dependent on EU institutions and member states. This is exemplified through the design of its internal governance structures, specifically its member state-dominated Management Board, and the process by which it operationalises its mandate: for it to be able to deliver, it must rely on close cooperation with member states.

The Management Board has pivotal roles in the steering functions as it must endorse the Country Guidance, for example. This renders these documents influential, as they draw on the Agency's expertise, but also require endorsement by a member state-dominated Management Board, even if they remain non-legally binding. At the same time, the largely intergovernmental character of the Management Board poses a challenge to the independence of the agency and to the objectivity of its products.

The (potential) added value of steering mechanisms

Despite the aforementioned challenges, the growing use of steering instruments under the Pact could respond to concrete structural challenges in EU migration governance. First, steering mechanisms can help to build the mutual trust necessary for solidarity to function in practice. Responsibility-sharing through relocations or financial contributions depends on member states implementing common rules consistently. Through the Annual Migration Management Cycle, common reporting structures, and agency-led networks, steering mechanisms create continuous interaction between national administrations and can contribute to a shared understanding of migratory pressure and solidarity needs. Importantly, these instruments are often co-produced with member states through Management Boards, expert networks, and operational cooperation, which can strengthen their legitimacy and acceptance.

Second, steering instruments allow for more rapid and continuous adjustment than traditional enforcement mechanisms. In a field characterised by fluctuating operational pressures, infringement procedures often come too late to avoid practical bottlenecks. Mechanisms such as the Migration Preparedness and Crisis Blueprint Network or the High-Level Network on Returns instead allow the Commission, agencies, and member states to identify obstacles, exchange information, and coor-

dinate operational responses in a timely manner. This reflects a broader shift from ex post correction towards continuous preparedness and operational management. Third, steering mechanisms can reduce divergent interpretations in national implementation practices. Instruments such as Asylum Agency Country Guidance, Convergence Reports, or practical guidance on border procedures provide common operational reference points for national administrations implementing the Pact. In this sense, steering contributes to limiting implementation through purely national interpretation and promotes greater administrative convergence across the Union.

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Finally, the increasing reliance on agencies, technical guidance, and operational coordination could also contribute to a partial depoliticisation of migration management. By framing sensitive issues such as returns, border procedures, or solidarity allocations and contributions through technical and administrative processes, steering mechanisms can facilitate cooperation in an area otherwise at risk of political tension or even deadlock. Yet precisely because these mechanisms stand to shape implementation in practice, ensuring transparency and accountability remains essential.

Soft enforcement through monitoring

At present, there are approximately 25 processes with monitoring potential across the EU asylum, migration, and border management policy landscape. These range from oversight entities and internal administrative frameworks to operational roles within EU migration agencies and the broader EU institutional ecosystem. The New Pact exemplifies this shift towards legally mandated oversight as it requires each member state to establish its own Independent National Monitoring Mechanism scrutinising respect for fundamental rights during the screening and border procedures.

The diversity of the mapped processes demonstrates that monitoring is multidimensional: while some processes focus on operational data, others target normative aspects. In some frameworks monitoring is the primary objective, whereas in others it is simply a by-product. This is the case, for instance, for accountability mechanisms that inherently require oversight to function. The common ground of the mapped processes is that through the leveraging of monitoring tasks they have as a main, or ancillary, objective the encouragement

of compliance. In addition, the various processes are strongly interdependent. This is also the case between some 'internal' processes of EU agencies and broader 'external' monitoring processes addressed to member states. This generates a number of challenges linked with soft enforcement through monitoring as currently designed and operationalised.

Challenges and limitations linked with monitoring mechanisms

The overload trap

The first challenge relates to the quantity of simultaneous monitoring processes related to migration, asylum, and integrated border management, and the extent of their scope and activities. Importantly, the effectiveness of many processes depends on the cooperation of member states. Under the New Pact, member states are required to establish an Independent National Monitoring Mechanism. Beyond its initial establishment, member states hold enduring responsibilities to maintain a functioning Independent National Monitoring Mechanism. Specifically, they must ensure the mechanism has sufficient capacity and means, guarantee its continued independence, criminalise screening-related fundamental rights violations under national law, and ensure that allegations trigger investigations and referrals for civil or criminal prosecution when necessary.

Next to this, member states face separate obligations under parallel monitoring frameworks, such as the new EU Asylum Agency Monitoring Mechanism. With its pilot phase now concluded, the formal EU Asylum Agency monitoring mechanism launches this year alongside the New Pact. Under this mechanism reviewing the operational and technical application of the Common European Asylum System (CEAS), member states must also cooperate: they must collaborate with the EU Asylum Agency by providing data, facilitate on-site visits, comment on recommendations, implement recommendations and report on their progress.¹⁹

In addition, these duties do not only materialise in processes explicitly aimed at monitoring migration policy implementation. Other administrative and accountability processes can de facto entail monitoring potential. This is the case, for example, with Frontex's Complaints Mechanism and Serious Incident Reporting Mechanism. These are primarily internal accountability and remedy-seeking tools that are "crucial for the Fundamental Rights Officer to monitor Frontex compliance".²⁰ As part of these mechanisms, however, member states are required to collaborate, report and take responsibility for following up on the conclusions of the monitoring. This has the potential to render this type of monitoring more effective compared to other mechanisms. However, further empirical research is necessary to ascertain whether this potential is fully reached in practice.

Effectively, the number and diversity of monitoring processes could result in an overload for agencies, member states and their national authorities and human rights structures tasked with collaborating, commenting or ensuring follow up.

The interdependence risk

Overlaps, links and dependencies between the simultaneous, yet distinct monitoring processes present another risk. This interplay is clearly exemplified in the Screening Regulation, Regulation (EU) 2024/1356), where the monitoring performed under four different frameworks interacts: the Independent National Monitoring Mechanism, the Schengen Evaluation and Monitoring Mechanism, the European Commission's financial monitoring, and the Parliament's Working Group on Schengen and Borders Scrutiny.

Once the Independent National Monitoring Mechanism reports on a member state's compliance with fundamental obligations during border screening, the Commission can use these findings to inform its monitoring under the Common Provisions Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2021/1060),²¹ which includes operationalisation of the funding frameworks in compliance with fundamental rights obligations. The rules laid down in the Common Provisions Regulation govern the management and attribution of various EU funds, including the Asylum and Migration Fund, the Internal Security Fund and funds related to the Border Management and Visa Instrument. On top of this, under two migration-related regulations,²² the Commission can suspend funding based on an evaluation report from the Schengen Evaluation and Monitoring Mechanism. Simultaneously, the European Parliament's working group exercises political scrutiny over both the implementation of the Common Provisions Regulation and the Schengen Evaluation and Monitoring Mechanism.

This interplay results in dependencies. Inaccuracy in a monitoring process could, for one, compromise the entire monitoring ecosystem. This could, in turn, jeopardise the use of monitoring as a credible complementary, or alternative, form of enforcement.

These overlaps constitute only the tip of the iceberg. Further interactions, such as the complementarity between the Schengen Evaluation and Monitoring Mechanism reports and Frontex's Vulnerability Assessment, add further levels of complexity. Moreover, the influence of the monitoring the European Ombudsman conducts on the budgetary supervision carried out by the European Parliament, also feeds into the multiplicity of entities providing information and assessments.

This interplay results in dependencies. Inaccuracy in a monitoring process could, for one, compromise the entire

monitoring ecosystem. This could, in turn, jeopardise the use of monitoring as a credible complementary, or alternative, form of enforcement. This risk is not hypothetical. In the case of the Screening Regulation, for example, concerns have been raised about the lack of mandatory procedural rules and a shared methodology for the Independent National Monitoring Mechanism.²³ The lack of a harmonised approach could result in incomparable and inaccurate reporting, negatively impacting other monitoring processes. Similar risks exist in processes outside of the New Pact. The Schengen Evaluation and Monitoring Mechanism has been deemed as being at particular risk of political interference.²⁴

The (potential) added value of monitoring mechanisms

Monitoring mechanisms can fulfil different purposes, often simultaneously.

Firstly, they ensure an oversight function: indicators and benchmarks allow for a diagnosis of both member state implementation and the effectiveness of the policy instruments monitored. This diagnosis provides the basis for decision-making, more effective cooperation, or to identify best practices.

Moreover, this use of collected data and knowledge underpins the coordinating function of monitoring: when promoting cooperation, it can advance mutual trust and understanding, coordinated action, and harmonised implementation.

Monitoring can also act in a preventive fashion. The prospect of being scrutinised, the use of comparative indicators, and, in the longer term, possible reputational damage, create normative pressure that influences member states' responses and implementation outcomes. This dual function, both preventive and coordinating, can position monitoring as a 'co-opetition' mechanism, which combines competition with cooperation and incentivises collaboration.

Monitoring reduces normative conflicts to data, which can, in turn, be used to (de)legitimise political choices.

Lastly, monitoring can also contribute to depoliticising the field of migration, asylum and border policy, which remains subject to political sensitivities. Indicators, viewed as objective and neutral, enable certain topics to be dealt with in a less confrontational manner. Monitoring reduces normative conflicts to data, which can, in turn, be used to (de)legitimise political choices. As a long and resource-intensive process, monitoring can also be a symbolic act that prevents a situation from escalating and generating (re)newed political tensions.

Prospects: Enhancing rights-compliant policy implementation through soft enforcement

Soft enforcement through steering and monitoring carries considerable potential to enhance rights-compliant policy implementation in the fields of EU asylum, migration, and integrated border management. However, several limitations and pitfalls surround its current design and practice. To realise soft enforcement's potential more fully, this Policy Brief puts forward the following recommendations:

→ Ensure clarity and transparency

In terms of *steering*, the European Commission should provide clarity as to the existing processes and mechanisms, including associated tasks, staffing composition, and interactions. Moreover, beyond their formal design, information on their working, outputs, and decisions should be made publicly available on a regular basis. This would enhance both the legitimacy of the processes and their outputs and prevent an accountability deficit.

In terms of *monitoring*, EU institutions, agencies, and member states should establish greater clarity on monitoring tasks, specifically their scope, objective(s) and practical implementation. This would reduce the risk of administrative or logistical fatigue and prevent the creation of another box-ticking exercise. In addition, the necessity and added value of each mechanism should be periodically reviewed. This is particularly needed when a mechanism is amended, or a new monitoring process is created.

→ Ensure meaningful synergies

In terms of *steering*, the European Commission should map out functional overlaps between the various steering processes. Overlap should be alleviated. Where parallel intersecting frameworks support effective synergies instead, the Commission should clarify how these different frameworks are to interact while avoiding overload. Where different assessments and outputs are combined into a single strategic evaluation, the European Commission should outline the respective weight and hierarchy (if any) of these different sources.

In terms of *monitoring*, a profound understanding of synergies between different processes is crucial. When dependencies exist, i) the different interactions should be clearly explained to the entities in charge; ii) appropriate methodological and qualitative safeguards such as internal or external quality control (see the point below) must be put in place; iii) the European Commission should outline how the outcomes of the different processes are concretely to be integrated.

➔ Ensure quality

To ensure the quality of *monitoring* and *steering*, the EU and member states should secure appropriate human, financial and logistical resources for all the actors involved. Investing in training and stakeholder exchanges will allow for soft enforcement to reach its full potential.

The involvement of external actors and independent expertise, including civil society, international organisations and academia, is also vital for ensuring the quality of *monitoring* and *steering* processes as well as their rights-compliant implementation focus. While soft enforcement is to some extent informal and technocratic, these processes are salient and can be politicised. Involving external actors in a number of monitoring missions under the different mechanisms (e.g. the Frontex Vulnerability Assessment or the Schengen Evaluation and Monitoring Mechanism) could help to reduce this risk, as could the submission of Country Guidance notes to expert external peer review.

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